

TRANSCRIPTOME ANALYSIS OF TWO OLIVE CULTIVARS IN RESPONSE TO *XYLELLA FASTIDIOSA* INFECTION. A. Giampetruzzi¹, M. Morelli², M. Saponari², G. Loconsole¹, M. Chiumentri², D. Boscia², V.N. Savino¹, G.P. Martelli¹, P. Saldarelli². ¹Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti (Di.S.S.P.A.) Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, 70126 Bari. ²CNR Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante (IPSP), SS Bari, 70126 Bari, Italy. E-mail: pasquale.saldarelli@ipsp.cnr.it

The CoDiRO strain of *Xylella fastidiosa* subsp. *pauciflora* (*Xfp*) is ravaging olive (*Olea europaea*) groves in southern Italy, causing a destructive disease denoted Olive Quick Decline Syndrome (OQDS). Field observations show that the *Xfp*-infected plants of the cv. Ogliarola salentina develop more severe symptoms than that of cv. Leccino. A global transcriptome profiling comparing the two olive cultivars, infected or not by *Xfp*, was performed to ascertain whether a tolerant condition of cv. Leccino exists, which could be exploited for lessening the economic impact of the disease on the local olive industry. The study revealed that 659 and 447 genes were differentially regulated upon *Xfp* infection, in cvs Leccino and Ogliarola salentina, respectively, whereas 512 genes resulted altered between the two infected cultivars. The analysis showed that plants of both cultivars perceive the presence of *Xfp*, mainly involving cell wall-associated proteins. The predominant response of cv. Leccino, which is missing in cv. Ogliarola salentina, consists on the up-regulation of genes encoding receptor-like kinases and receptor-like proteins. This different transcriptome response determines a lower pathogen concentration in the cv. Leccino, suggesting that it may harbor genetic constituents and/or regulatory elements which counteract *Xfp* infection. These findings suggest that cv. Leccino is endowed with an intrinsic tolerance to *Xfp*, which makes it eligible for further studies aimed at investigating molecular pathways underlying its different defense response.

POTATO SPINDLE TUBER VIROID UPREGULATES DNA METHYLATION-RELATED GENES AND ANTAGONIZES THE INFECTIVITY AND THE ACCUMULATION OF A GEMINIVIRUS. E.M. Torchetti¹, M. Pegoraro², B. Navarro¹, M. Catoni³, E. Noris², F. Di Serio¹. ¹Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante, Bari, Italy. ²Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche, Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante, Torino, Italy. ³University of Cambridge, The Sainsbury Laboratory, Cambridge, United Kingdom. E-mail: francesco.diserio@ipsp.cnr.it

Tomato is a natural host of *Potato spindle tuber viroid* (PSTVd) and *Tomato yellow leaf curl Sardinia virus* (TYLCSV), which are representative members of pospiviroids (infectious non-coding circular RNAs) and geminiviruses (single-stranded DNA viruses), respectively. While molecular events during infection have been explored separately for each one of these two nuclear replicating pathogens, plant responses during mixed infections are unknown. In this context, dissection of DNA methylation pathway is particularly interesting because it is well known that plants may methylate viral DNA to impair geminivirus infection, while whether viroids interfere with host DNA methylation pathways is unknown. Exploiting an experimental system based on PSTVd and TYLCSV co-infecting the same tomato plant, and applying qRT-PCR, methylation-sensitive restriction and bisulfite conversion assays, we found that: i) when plants were co-infected, TYLCSV infectivity and accumulation were strongly impaired, indicating an antagonistic action of PSTVd; ii) PSTVd alone or in double infection with TYLCSV significantly upregulated the expression of key genes governing DNA methylation in plants; iii) PSTVd promoted a strong hypermethylation of TYLCSV DNA in tomato plants co-infected by both pathogens, thus supporting a mechanistic link with the antagonism

of the viroid on the virus during co-infection. Besides providing the first solid evidence that a viroid may interfere with host regulatory networks involved in DNA methylation, these data open new perspectives on the possible involvement of viroid-induced epigenetic changes in plant responses against other biotic and abiotic stresses.

DISTINCT EFFECTS OF TOMBUSVIRAL p19 RNA SILENCING SUPPRESSOR ON SMALL RNA MEDIATED PATHWAYS IN PLANTS. L. Kontra^{1,2}, T. Csorba¹, M. Tavazza³, A. Luciolli³, R. Tavazza³, S. Moxon⁴, V. Tisza¹, A. Medzihradsky¹, M. Turina⁵, J. Burgyán¹. ¹National Agricultural Research and Innovation Centre, Agricultural Biotechnology Institute, Szent-Györgyi A. 4., Gödöllő H-2100, Hungary. ²Szent Istvan University, Gödöllő, Hungary. ³UTAGRI Centro Ricerche Casaccia, Agenzia Nazionale per le Nuove Tecnologie, l'Energia e lo Sviluppo Economico Sostenibile, Rome, Italy. ⁴The Genome Analysis Centre, Norwich, UK. ⁵National Research Council, Institute for Sustainable Plant Protection, Torino, Italy. E-mail: burgyan@abc.hu

Viral suppressors of RNA silencing (VSRs) are specialized arms deployed by viruses to neutralize the antiviral RNA silencing plant defense mechanism. Since the endogenous and antiviral functions of RNA silencing pathway rely on common components, it was suggested that VSRs interfere with endogenous silencing pathway contributing to viral symptom development. In this work, we aimed to understand the effects of the tombusviral p19 VSR on endogenous and antiviral silencing during genuine virus infection. To this end, we generated a *Nicotiana benthamiana* plant (p19syn) capable of sustaining the ectopic expression of the *Cymbidium ringspot virus* (CymRSV) p19 upon infection with a suppressor-deficient CymRSV (Cym19stop). By using wt and p19syn plants in combination with CymRSV and Cym19stop, we were able to analyze the effects of p19 provided “*in trans*” and “*in cis*” during the viral invasion of the plant. We showed that ectopically expressed p19 sequesters endogenous small RNAs (sRNAs) in the absence, but not in the presence of virus infection. Our presented data question the generalized model in which the sequestration of endogenous sRNAs by the viral suppressor contributes to the viral symptom development. We further showed that p19 preferentially enriches the perfectly-paired ds-viral small interfering RNAs (vsiRNAs) but does not select based on their sequence or the type of the 5' nucleotide. Finally, using AGO1- and AGO2-immunoprecipitation experiments we observed that p19 specifically compromises vsRNAs' loading into AGO1 but not AGO2. Since antiviral silencing is strongly inhibited by p19, this suggests that AGO1 is the main effector protein against tombusviruses.

IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERISATION OF THE GRAPEVINE ATL GENE FAMILY AND FUNCTIONAL ROLE OF AN ATL GENE FROM *VITIS RIPARIA* IN DOWNY MILDEW RESISTANCE. P. Ariani¹, A. Regaiolo¹, A. Lovato¹, A. Giorgetti¹, A. Porceddu², S. Camiolo², D. Wong³, S. Castellari³, C. Zadra⁴, E. Vandelle¹, A. Polverari¹. ¹Università degli Studi di Verona, Dipartimento di Biotechnologie, Ca' Vignal 1, strada le Grazie 15 - 37134 Verona, Italy. ²Università degli Studi di Sassari, Dipartimento di Agraria, SACEG, Sassari, Italy. ³University of British Columbia, Wine Research Centre, Vancouver, Canada. ⁴Università di Perugia, Dipartimento di Scienze Agroambientali e della Produzione Vegetale, Sez. Chimica Agraria, Perugia, Italy. E-mail: elodiegenevieve.vandelle@uniivr.it

Plasmopara viticola is the causal agent of downy mildew, one of the most economically important grapevine diseases. In an attempt to decipher the resistance mechanisms evolved in naturally resistant